

No Peace Without Democracy, No Democracy Without Peace: Comparative Perspectives on Political Transitions in Africa

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Abstract

This article analyzes the interlinked dynamics between peace and democracy through a comparative study of three African cases: Ghana, Tunisia, and Sierra Leone. Challenging linear models that view peace as a prerequisite for democratization, it argues that democratic practices and institutions can themselves be sources of lasting peace. Using a qualitative approach and a moderately contrasting case selection, the study examines how inclusive governance, civil society engagement, and institutional legitimacy have shaped both democratic resilience and post-conflict stability. By connecting empirical observations with theoretical debates on democratic peace and peacebuilding, the article puts forward the hypothesis that “paving the way to peace is also paving the way to democracy; investing in democracy means investing in sustainable peace.” It presents an analytical framework for a better understanding of political transitions in fragile or hybrid regimes. Peace and democracy emerge as closely intertwined processes whose stability depends on their parallel and complementary development—a particularly critical imperative in contexts marked by historical ruptures, weak state capacity, and recurrent political violence.

Keywords: *Political transitions; Transitology; Peacebuilding; Democracy; Africa; Military coups; Comparative politics; State fragility; Democratic legitimacy*

Introduction

“Positive peace requires not only the absence of direct violence but also the presence of equitable structures.”
Johan Galtung (Peace by Peaceful Means, 1996)

In December 2024, Ghana once again reaffirmed its status as a regional leader in democratic consolidation. For the fourth straight time, the country facilitated a peaceful transfer of power between opposing parties following credible elections—this time between incumbent President Nana Akufo-Addo and his rival, former President John Dramani Mahama. This seamless transition sharply contrasts with the contested and sometimes violent electoral processes seen elsewhere on the continent. Similarly, Tunisia’s post-2011 transition—especially driven by the mediation efforts of the National Dialogue Quartet, which received the Nobel Peace Prize in 2015—helped the country avoid civil war, establish a constitutional transition, and foster a pluralistic political environment. These experiences highlight a key but still underexamined question in the literature on political transitions: Is peace a necessary precondition for democracy, or can democracy itself establish the foundation for lasting peace?

In both African political discourse and international theoretical debates, peace and democracy are often treated as distinct, sometimes sequential goals. Peace is typically framed in terms of security—cessation of violence, restoration of order, signing of ceasefire agreements—while democracy is associated with institutional forms such as elections, the separation of powers, and the rule of law. This linear understanding, dominant in post-conflict policy prescriptions, assumes that peace must precede democratization. Yet, such dichotomous thinking fails to capture the complexity of transitional dynamics, especially in fragile states where regime change, social instability, and electoral competition are deeply intertwined. Contrary to this linear view, this article argues that peace and democracy should be seen as co-constitutive processes, capable of mutually supporting each other in post-conflict settings. In societies characterized by weak state institutions, ongoing polarization, and low levels of institutional legitimacy, the sequencing dilemma—whether to prioritize pacification

before democratization—remains an important issue. However, instead of framing these aspects as oppositional, this study adopts the following interpretive perspective:

“Laying the groundwork for peace is laying the groundwork for democracy; investing in democracy is investing in sustainable peace.”

From this perspective, the article compares three African trajectories—Ghana, Tunisia, and Sierra Leone—analyzing how peace and democracy intersect in each case. The goal is to find the conditions where democratic practices can promote political stability and, conversely, how peacebuilding can create an environment suitable for democratic consolidation.

This inquiry is organized into six sections. The first introduces the central hypothesis and research question. The second provides a thorough review of the relevant literature, including theories of democratic peace, debates on post-conflict sequencing, and perspectives from African political experiences. The third section outlines the analytical framework and methodological approach used in the comparative case studies. Section four offers an in-depth analysis of the three cases. Section five presents a comparative synthesis. Finally, the sixth section summarizes the findings and provides policy recommendations for those involved in democratic transitions and peacebuilding across Africa.

II. Literature Review: Theories and Debates

The relationship between peace and democracy has been widely debated in the fields of international relations, political science, and transition studies. This section reviews the main theoretical frameworks that have influenced this discussion, with a focus on their relevance and limitations in modern African contexts. It is divided into four parts: (1) an overview of classical theories of “democratic peace”; (2) an analysis of approaches that see peace as a prerequisite for democracy; (3) perspectives that consider democracy itself as a catalyst for sustainable peace; and (4) a comparative analysis of different theoretical frameworks on the peace–democracy relationship.

1. Theories of “Democratic Peace”

The concept of democratic peace is one of the most influential ideas in modern international relations. It claims that democratic governments are much less likely to go to war with each other than non-democratic ones. Although well established in today’s political science literature, this idea has roots in Enlightenment philosophy, especially in Immanuel Kant’s important essay *Perpetual Peace* (1795/2003). Kant believed that representative republics, where citizens bear the costs of war, are less likely to support it. These representative systems, by adding procedural rules, serve as institutional brakes on leaders’ decisions to declare war.

This normative foundation was reinterpreted in the 20th century through an empirical perspective, especially in the work of Michael Doyle (1986), who formalized the concept of “liberal peace,” and Bruce Russett (1993), whose statistical research showed that established democracies rarely go to war with one another. These scholars do not claim that democracies are naturally pacifist—many have fought wars against non-democracies—but instead highlight a strong empirical pattern: democracies seldom fight each other. This finding supports a liberal school of thought that considers the worldwide spread of democracy as promoting a more peaceful international order.

According to Doyle (1986), the pacifying effect of liberal regimes mainly comes from the normative ethos of political liberalism, which encourages mutual respect for legitimacy, institutionalized tolerance, and recognition of political autonomy. Russett (1993), on the other hand, highlights the institutional mechanisms inherent in democratic systems—such as separation of powers, freedom of the press, governmental transparency, and electoral accountability—which increase the political costs of starting a war and thus decrease its likelihood. In this perspective, liberal democracy creates an environment conducive to peaceful cooperation.

However, the empirical link between democracy and peace heavily depends on one key condition: the successful consolidation of democratic institutions. This point is central to the critique made by Mansfield and Snyder (1995), who warn against the dangers of transitional democracies. In their important article “*Democratization and the Danger of War*”, they argue that regimes in the early phases of democratization—yet still fragile—are especially vulnerable to instability and conflict. Introducing pluralistic elections too soon in

areas with deep identity divisions and a political culture that lacks compromise can worsen tensions instead of reducing them.

Mansfield and Snyder (1995) also popularized the concepts of "illiberal democracy" and "electoral authoritarianism" to describe hybrid regimes that have the formal features of democratic institutions but operate through authoritarian methods. In such systems, elections often become high-stakes zero-sum battles, lacking fair rules and independent oversight. Political victory is viewed as gaining exclusive access to state resources, turning electoral processes into survival struggles. This can lead to post-election violence and weaken public trust in democratic governance.

Empirical cases from Africa highlight these issues. In Kenya, the contested 2007 elections led to widespread interethnic violence, killing over a thousand people (Mueller, 2008). In Côte d'Ivoire, refusing to accept electoral defeat after the 2010 presidential elections ignited a renewed civil war (International Crisis Group, 2011). Nigeria experienced a serious political crisis in 1993 when the military regime nullified transparent and competitive elections (Lewis, 1994). These examples show the risks of holding elections without proper institutional safeguards to guarantee legitimacy, fairness, and accountability.

Ultimately, these critiques do not undermine the overall logic of the democratic peace thesis but rather specify its conditions for application. Sustainable peace is not guaranteed solely by holding elections; it relies on a stable democratic environment based on inclusion, institutional legitimacy, the rule of law, and a culture of political compromise.

2. Peace as a Prerequisite for Democracy? A Critical Reappraisal of the Liberal Paradigm

In international post-conflict peacebuilding efforts, one paradigm has dominated since the end of the Cold War: "*liberal peacebuilding*". As an intellectual extension of the democratic peace theory (Kant, 1795/2003; Doyle, 1986), this normative framework assumes that sustainable peace can be achieved through the simultaneous promotion of democratic institutional reforms, economic liberalization, and pluralist electoral processes. Widely supported by the United Nations and international donors, this approach has guided interventions in diverse contexts such as Bosnia and Herzegovina, Timor-Leste, and Liberia (Paris, 2004).

However, this approach has come under increasing scrutiny, particularly in the systematic critique advanced by Roland Paris. In *“At War’s End: Building Peace After Civil Conflict”*, Paris (2004) highlights the limitations of liberal orthodoxy, which often universalizes Western institutional models while disregarding local dynamics. The imposition of rigid electoral timelines, neoliberal reforms, and standardized governance structures in deeply fragmented societies can produce effects contrary to those intended—namely, renewed violence, increased polarization, and the erosion of state legitimacy.

Empirical examples illustrate these adverse outcomes. In Bosnia, the 1996 elections reinforced ethnonational divisions rather than transcending them (Paris, 1997). In Timor-Leste, tensions between societal expectations and institutional weakness led to persistent instability. In Liberia, despite significant international support, democratization efforts were undermined by clientelism and weak administrative capacity.

In response to these shortcomings, Paris proposes a more incremental strategy: “institutionalization before liberalization.” This sequential approach emphasizes the need to first rebuild the foundational elements of the state—security, public services, and the rule of law—before initiating complex democratic reforms.

Similarly, Ottaway (2003) warns that premature democratization may undermine stabilization objectives. In settings where institutions are still weak and social divisions are clear, political competition can fuel rather than reduce tensions. She recommends focusing on state consolidation as a foundation for sustainable democratic progress.

The work of Chesterman (2004) and Barnett (2010) reinforces this cautious stance. In countries such as Afghanistan, Iraq, and South Sudan, international actors chose centralized or technocratic transitional administrations, deliberately delaying elections to prevent early destabilization. While these strategies helped achieve short-term stability, they also risked limiting democratic momentum.

African cases like Rwanda and Angola illustrate this pattern. In Kigali, the Rwandan Patriotic Front (RPF) created a stable yet authoritarian political system, prioritizing security over political openness (Reyntjens, 2016). In Angola, the postwar era was characterized by the centralization of power under the MPLA, with elections postponed for several years and held within a framework of ongoing dominance.

These configurations raise a fundamental normative question: can an order characterized by repression of dissent, absence of public debate,

and exclusion of critical voices truly be called “peace”? While they may prevent the immediate return of violence, such authoritarian paths cast doubt on their long-term viability.

Instead of viewing peace and democracy as straightforward and universal stages, these critiques promote a more nuanced understanding of political transitions as complex and context-dependent processes. The timing, order, and societal acceptance of reforms must be carefully managed. Otherwise, there's a risk of replacing open conflict with an imposed and fragile peace.

3. Democratic Transitions as Drivers of Peacebuilding

Unlike sequential approaches that advocate for a fixed sequence between peace and democracy, a growing body of scholarship emphasizes the inherent ability of democratic transitions to act as tools of pacification. This view does not see democratization as naturally destabilizing but instead examines the specific ways it is carried out. In this perspective, political opening alone does not cause instability; instead, instability stems from a lack of inclusiveness, transparency, or institutional strength in transitional processes (Hyden, 2006; Bratton & van de Walle, 1997).

This interpretation is also present—albeit more nuanced—in Roland Paris’s work (2004). While critical of the standardized, one-size-fits-all model of liberal peacebuilding, Paris nonetheless recognizes the stabilizing potential of democratic institutions when they are adapted to local contexts. Democracy, from this perspective, is not an exportable model to be imposed rapidly, but a political process rooted in compromise, governmental accountability, and the gradual internalization of pluralist norms by society.

Empirical contributions from scholars such as Nic Cheeseman (2015), Catherine Boone (2003), and Robert Mattes et al. (2010) reinforce this argument. Their research highlights the importance of credible institutional mechanisms—such as independent electoral commissions, impartial judicial bodies, recognition of party pluralism, and balanced decentralization frameworks—in channeling political tensions. When these mechanisms are perceived as legitimate, they can reduce confrontational dynamics, provide peaceful avenues for conflict resolution, and build public trust in the political system.

To be sure, many African democracies continue to exhibit hybrid characteristics, combining formal electoral competition with authoritarian practices (Levitsky & Way, 2010). Yet even within such

incomplete or ambiguous regimes, democracy often plays a regulatory role—serving as a pressure-release valve by offering spaces, however limited, for political dialogue and civic participation.

The trajectories of Ghana and Tunisia illustrate this pattern. In Ghana, the gradual development of an electoral culture, respect for constitutional term limits, and the peaceful resolution of political conflicts through courts have fostered long-term stability (Gyimah-Boadi, 2009). In Tunisia, the National Dialogue Quartet played a key role in easing tensions after the 2011 revolution by promoting an inclusive agreement among divided political groups (Allal, 2016).

These cases indicate that democracy can, in certain contexts, serve not only as an eventual outcome of peace but also as a mechanism for establishing peace early in the transition process. When inclusive, incremental, and grounded in institutions, democracy can function as a vehicle for pacification, even in initially volatile environments.

Ultimately, this reading encourages us to move beyond strict dichotomies between peace and democracy. It promotes a flexible understanding of their relationship—one that views them not as separate stages but as interconnected, mutually shaping processes. This hypothesis is what the rest of this study aims to examine through a comparative analysis of transition paths in Ghana, Tunisia, and Sierra Leone. Before continuing, however, a comparative overview of the different ways peace and democracy interact is necessary.

4. Comparative Theoretical Approaches to the Peace–Democracy Nexus

The literature on the relationship between peace and democracy in post-conflict settings is organized around three main theoretical perspectives. Each is based on specific assumptions about timing, institutional mechanisms, and the conditions necessary for successful transitions. Rather than forming rigid or mutually exclusive paradigms, these approaches represent different analytical sensitivities toward the causal links between political stability and democratization.

A. The Co-Institutive (Liberal) Approach: Building Peace Through Democracy

Rooted in the Kantian tradition (Perpetual Peace, 1795) and supported by empirical studies like Doyle (1986) and Russett (1993),

the liberal approach views democracy as a natural means of promoting peace. According to this perspective, democratic regimes—because of their institutional structure (separation of powers, transparency, and accountability)—are less likely to resort to violence, especially in their dealings with other democracies.

This paradigm inspired the liberal peacebuilding strategies promoted by international institutions during the 1990s, aiming to establish peace and democracy through simultaneous structural reforms. However, its prescriptive nature and limited sensitivity to endogenous dynamics have drawn significant criticism. In fragile settings, the mechanical transplantation of liberal institutions often increased polarization, enabled elite capture of state structures, or reignited latent tensions.

B. The Sequential Approach: Peace Before Democracy

In response to the limitations of the co-institutive model, a second theoretical orientation promotes a more gradualist view of temporal development. Most notably articulated by Paris (2004) under the strategy of "institutionalization before liberalization," this approach underscores the importance of rebuilding core state functions—such as territorial control, sovereign institutions, and bureaucratic capacity—before initiating significant democratic reforms.

Its central premise is that democracy cannot take root without a minimum level of institutional stability. Countries such as Angola and Rwanda exemplify this path: in both cases, authoritarian centralization was deliberately prioritized to achieve peace, often at the expense of political liberties but in the name of improved governability. The goal is not to rush into imposing democracy but to make it sustainable over the long term.

C. The Co-Developmental Approach: Democracy as a Driver of Peace

A third perspective presents a more dynamic and context-aware view of the peace–democracy link. Supported by scholars like Hyden (2006), Bratton and van de Walle (1997), and Cheeseman (2015), this approach sees democracy not as a threat in post-conflict settings but as a possible tool for peacebuilding—if it is inclusive, step-by-step, and locally rooted.

Its core hypothesis is that conflict arises not from democracy itself but from its flawed implementation or instrumentalization by political elites. Credible democratic institutions—such as independent electoral

commissions, functional constitutional courts, and the effective recognition of political pluralism—can serve as channels for conflict regulation. Post-2011 Tunisia and Ghana are illustrative of this logic: in both cases, inter-elite dialogue, institutional inclusiveness, and adherence to the rules of the democratic game helped contain tensions and laid the foundations for durable political stability.

D. Toward an Integrated and Contextual Reading

These three approaches present different visions of the peace–democracy relationship: liberal simultaneity, cautious sequencing, or progressive co-development. All highlight the ongoing dilemmas faced by post-crisis interventions: should priority go to security or participation, stability or openness, governance effectiveness or popular legitimacy?

Despite their differences, a growing consensus emerges: the importance of context, institutional flexibility, and long-term paths. The challenge is not just to choose between sequencing and simultaneity but to see transitions as connected, changing, and multi-layered processes that need strategies tailored to specific contexts.

This study is grounded in an integrated and comparative perspective. By analyzing three African cases, it aims to determine whether the observed empirical patterns support, challenge, or reshape these theoretical frameworks.

Table 1. Theoretical Perspectives on the Peace–Democracy Link

Theoretical Approach	Core Assumption	Temporal Logic	Associated Risks	Key Scholars
Democratic Peace Theory	Consolidated democracies are more likely to maintain peace, especially among themselves.	Peace as an outcome of democracy	Fragile democratic transitions; rushed or premature elections	Kant (1795), Doyle (1986), Russett (1993)
Sequential Liberal Peacebuilding	Peacebuilding (order, institutions, security) must precede democratic reforms.	Peace before democracy	Authoritarian entrenchment; exclusion of pluralism; legitimacy without participation	Paris (2004), Chesterman (2004), Ottaway (2003)

Theoretical Approach	Core Assumption	Temporal Logic	Associated Risks	Key Scholars
Democratic Transitions as Vehicles for Peace	Well-designed democratic institutions can serve as frameworks for sustaining peace.	Co-institution of peace and democracy	Institutional weakness; lack of inclusivity; political polarization	Hyden (2006), Bratton & van de Walle (1997), Cheeseman (2015), Tchankoumi (2025)

The table above compares three main theoretical approaches to the peace–democracy link, each with different assumptions, timelines, and risks. The Democratic Peace Theory, based on Kantian ideas and developed empirically by Doyle (1986) and Russett (1993), argues that established democracies are generally more peaceful, especially with other democracies. It sees peace as a result of building democratic institutions, though it faces criticism for ignoring the instability of transitional regimes and the risks of early elections. In contrast, the Sequential Liberal Peacebuilding approach—represented by Paris (2004), Chesterman (2004), and Ottaway (2003)—advocates for establishing order and state capacity before moving toward democracy. While this model focuses on stability, it can also risks leading to authoritarianism and limiting democratic involvement. A third, more context-aware view sees Democratic Transitions as Tools for Peace, suggesting that inclusive and credible democratic institutions can promote stability in fragile states. Supported by scholars like Hyden (2006), Bratton and van de Walle (1997), Cheeseman (2015), and Tchankoumi (2025), this approach encourages co-building peace and democracy, while recognizing the weaknesses of fragile institutions and elite polarization. Overall, these approaches highlight the different theories and policy debates surrounding the order and design of political transitions after conflicts.

III. Analytical Framework and Methodology

This article uses a qualitative comparative approach to explore the conditions under which peace and democracy can support each other during African political transitions. To go beyond the strict divide between "peace first" and "democracy later" models, the study develops an analytical framework that includes historical paths, institutional structures, and social dynamics.

1. Methodological Rationale

The chosen method is based on a nuanced comparative approach that relies on moderate contrasts. Instead of comparing vastly different cases, the goal is to examine contexts that, despite notable differences—such as the type of previous conflicts, institutional structures, or levels of political liberalization—also have common features. This approach avoids overgeneralization while allowing for the identification of insights that can be applied across cases.

The selected cases involve national trajectories characterized by internal conflict or significant political change, yet they display commonalities that help reveal shared mechanisms. For example, colonial legacies have left enduring marks on administrative systems, territorial borders, and perceptions of authority. Likewise, regional dynamics—including the spread of political models, interstate cooperation, and international mediation—along with external pressures from donors and international organizations, serve as important external factors.

Within this framework, the comparison aims to identify recurring mechanisms that either promote or obstruct the co-creation of peace and democracy. The goal is to understand how certain institutional setups stabilize political relations in fragile societies and under what conditions political inclusion acts as a catalyst for peace or, alternatively, a source of renewed tension. This analysis relies on close examinations of historical contexts, actor configurations, and domestic dynamics, while also questioning the influence of external factors in reshaping political balances.

Ultimately, this comparative approach allows for a more precise understanding of democratic transitions by considering the complexity of post-conflict settings. It thus facilitates a targeted analysis of the political and institutional factors that support the development of a legitimate and peaceful order.

2. Case Selection

The study examines three countries: Ghana, Tunisia, and Sierra Leone. Each one showcases a different setup of the peace-democracy relationship.

- Ghana exemplifies successful democratic consolidation after a period of military rule. It shows how credible electoral

institutions, an active civil society, and peaceful power shifts can foster long-term political stability.

- Tunisia remains the only successful democratic transition to come out of the Arab uprisings, where a process of national dialogue prevented civil war. The role of the National Dialogue Quartet highlights the potential of democratic compromise as a path to peace.
- Sierra Leone, a post-conflict society shaped by a devastating civil war, gradually rebuilt its democracy under international supervision. This process led to the emergence of a relatively stable and pluralistic political system.

As previously mentioned, these cases were chosen based on a moderate level of contrast to highlight key challenges faced in African contexts: endogenous transition (Ghana), revolutionary compromise (Tunisia), and post-conflict reconstruction (Sierra Leone). This selection enables the study to focus on key mechanisms while controlling for contextual biases. However, the approach has limitations. On one hand, emphasizing relatively “successful” cases may minimize patterns of failure (e.g., Mali). On the other hand, the uniqueness of each transition warrants caution in making broad generalizations, especially concerning informal variables such as clientelism or militarization. These limitations point to future research directions that include more conflict-prone or hybrid cases.

3. Data Sources, Variables, and Analytical Axes

This study relies on a qualitative review of documentary sources, including academic literature, reports from international organizations (United Nations, African Union, International IDEA), official documents (such as constitutions and electoral laws), and contributions from civil society (like communiqués, testimonies, and local surveys). These materials offer a layered perspective on events, institutional arrangements, and socio-political dynamics in each country.

The analysis is organized around four main variables:

- **Sequence of events:** Does peace come before democracy, or is the opposite true?
- **Role of political institutions:** e.g., electoral commissions, constitutional courts, transitional justice mechanisms.

- **Influence of domestic actors:** e.g., political parties, religious leaders, trade unions, civic associations.
- **Impact of international partners:** e.g., peacekeeping missions, reconstruction aid, democratic conditionalities.

These variables enable the study to compare not just outcomes but also the processes by which peace and democracy reinforce each other.

Building on this analytical framework and methodological basis, the article now proceeds to a detailed analysis of the chosen cases. Through this empirical study, it aims to assess how institutional dynamics, actor configurations, and event sequences influence the strengthening, articulation, or weakening of the relationship between peacebuilding and democratization. Each case will be examined using the key variables identified, within a comparative approach intended to identify patterns, differences, and applicable insights.

IV. Case Studies

1. Ghana: Post-Authoritarian Democratic Consolidation

Ghana is a key example often cited in studies of African democratic paths. The country's political history includes a series of military coups and authoritarian rulers from the 1960s through the early 1990s. A major turning point occurred with the adoption of the 1992 Constitution, which started a new period of institutional stability marked by multiparty politics, regular elections, and official recognition of civil liberties. Unlike many African countries where transitions have been delayed or reversed, Ghana has managed to not only hold elections but also maintain a consistent pattern of peaceful power transfers—shown in the elections of 2000, 2008, 2016, and 2024—without major breaks in the constitutional order.

This relative political stability cannot be solely credited to successful electoral processes. It is supported by a specific institutional framework where key bodies—like the Independent Electoral Commission and the Supreme Court—play essential roles in overseeing the political landscape. The Electoral Commission is seen as both highly competent and politically impartial, gaining legitimacy across party lines even during disputed elections. Likewise, the Supreme Court has established itself as a credible judge in electoral conflicts, especially when handling post-election petitions. These institutional structures are bolstered by an

active and alert civil society made up of religious groups, civic organizations, and independent media, which together serve as informal but powerful counterbalances to political authority. This social fabric acts as a safeguard against political unrest by raising the costs of authoritarian control. As Gyimah-Boadi (2009) points out, Ghana's stability relies less on perfect institutions and more on a tradition of legal debate and citizen-led mediation.

However, underlying structural fragilities remain—notably the persistent presence of clientelist networks (Gyimah-Boadi, 2015). Beyond institutional design, Ghana illustrates a strategy of partial co-optation of elites from the former regime into the emerging pluralistic order. This gradual integration—rather than exclusion or radical rupture—has helped neutralize dynamics of political vengeance or armed resistance, which have destabilized other post-authoritarian contexts. The legacy of military rule has not been erased but reconfigured, with the armed forces now playing a normalized role subordinate to civilian authority.

Ghana thus provides a clear example of democratic consolidation serving not only as a normative goal but also as a means for sustainable peacebuilding. Confidence in the rules of the game, the consistency of electoral processes, and the perception of fairness across different societal groups lower the incentives to use violence in political disputes. The unique aspect of the Ghanaian model arguably lies in this interaction of credible institutions, gradual elite inclusion, and active civil society participation within the West African political scene.

As Gyimah-Boadi (2009) aptly summarizes, "*Ghana shows that an African democracy can work when domestic actors take ownership of the rules of the game—but this requires constant vigilance against authoritarian backsliding*"; "*Despite these achievements, Ghanaian democracy remains undermined by clientelism and corruption. Political alternation has not always led to substantive policy change, as elites continue to perpetuate neo-patrimonial practices*" (Gyimah-Boadi, 2015).

2. Tunisia: National Dialogue and Post-Revolutionary Transition

Tunisia symbolizes one of the most important post-authoritarian political shifts in the modern Arab-Muslim world. Coming out of the upheavals of the Arab Spring, Tunisia's transition is notable for

avoiding institutional collapse and civil war—unlike Libya, Syria, or Yemen. Despite the fall of the Ben Ali regime in January 2011 bringing major political uncertainty, it did not lead to total state breakdown. Instead, moderation and balancing strategies—especially the mediation led by the National Dialogue Quartet—proved essential.

This unprecedented coalition—comprising the UGTT (trade union), UTICA (employers' federation), the Tunisian Human Rights League, and the Bar Association—established itself as a moral authority capable of restoring space for negotiation when polarization between Ennahda and secular opponents threatened to derail the constitutional process. Following political assassinations in 2013 and escalating security tensions, Tunisia nearly reached the breaking point. However, instead of descending into violence, a consensual solution emerged: a revised transition schedule, a provisional technocratic government, and shared procedural rules. The awarding of the 2015 Nobel Peace Prize to the Quartet highlighted the international recognition of non-partisan actors' vital role in post-revolutionary stabilization. As Larbi Sadiki (2020) succinctly observes, "*The Tunisian Quartet did not invent consensus, but institutionalized a culture of compromise in a context where politics had become synonymous with brutal confrontation.*" It succeeded by translating street-level demands into rules that elites could accept.

Tunisia's path shows that in revolutionary settings, democracy goes beyond just elections and can function as a structured space for mediating deeply conflicting worldviews—if opponents agree to the idea of compromise. The 2014 Constitution, crafted through intense negotiations amid open tensions, reflects this combination of Islamic, secular, progressive, and conservative ideas. Mutual recognition, not unilateral victory, guided the institutional design they adopted.

However, this relative calm should not be mistaken for a permanent or simple process. Recent years have exposed structural weaknesses: ongoing government instability, sluggish economic growth, declining trust in political parties and institutions, and the resurgence of authoritarian rhetoric by executive leaders. The election of President Kais Saïed and the subsequent centralization of power highlight ongoing tensions between the desire for order and the hope for inclusive governance. As Amin Allal (2016) notes, "*The 2014 Constitution enshrined individual freedoms but did not bridge the divide between coastal regions and the interior. Those 'forgotten by the revolution' continue to fuel resentment exploited by populists like Kais Saïed.*"

In summary, Tunisia offers a complex yet insightful example of the connection between peace and democracy in post-revolutionary

contexts. It shows that political stability can be maintained temporarily through dialogue and compromise. However, its long-term viability depends on the system's ability to deliver tangible results in social justice, political participation, and security. Democracy can indeed act as a calming force—it requires ongoing commitment from political, institutional, and civil society actors to prevent it from becoming a hollow procedural form.

3. Sierra Leone: Democratic Reconstruction After Civil War

Sierra Leone offers a clear example of post-conflict political rebuilding in a setting of severe violence and near-total state collapse. The civil war, which lasted from 1991 to 2002, left behind a shattered institutional framework, a divided society, and a militarized informal economy. The 1999 Lomé Peace Accord, followed by the significant intervention of the United Nations Mission in Sierra Leone (UNAMSIL), started a gradual process of peacebuilding. This reconstruction was organized around concurrent phases: disarmament, demobilization, and reintegration (DDR) of combatants, and the rebuilding of elected institutions.

The 2002 general elections—despite critiques of premature timing—were widely seen as a strong sign of political normalization. They were accompanied by the implementation of transitional justice mechanisms, particularly the Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC), which aimed to document wartime atrocities, restore national cohesion, and promote collective memory work. This dual approach—electoral and memorial—fits with the liberal peacebuilding model supported by international donors, which considers rapid democratization a key step toward stabilization.

Nonetheless, Sierra Leone's trajectory remains deeply ambivalent. On one hand, the country has experienced a degree of institutional regularity since 2002. Multiparty elections have taken place every five years, leading to peaceful power transitions—particularly in 2007 and 2018. The National Electoral Commission (NEC), supported logistically and financially by international partners, has gained technical credibility, although allegations of electoral fraud and pre-electoral tensions persist.

Conversely, power remains highly personalized, marked by resilient neo-patrimonial structures, dependence on international aid, and chronically weak public services. As Olonisakin (2008) argues, while technically efficient, the NEC suffers from a legitimacy deficit due to

its reliance on external funding. The institutions established under international supervision—such as the Special Court for Sierra Leone and the NEC—highlight both the benefits and limitations of externally driven governance. Although these bodies restored procedural legality, their weak local foundation and dependence on foreign financing cast doubt on their long-term sustainability.

Furthermore, communal logics—often exploited by political elites—continue to foster divisions that threaten national unity. Although celebrated as a UN success story, Sierra Leone’s peace remains delicate without deep structural reforms (Olonisakin, 2008).

However, the Sierra Leonean case shows that even in situations of severe institutional collapse, peace can lay a groundwork for slow democratic progress—if there is ongoing international support and real domestic political commitment to rebuilding. The process is delicate, reversible, and uneven, but it offers opportunities to break cycles of recurring violence.

When comparing the experiences of Ghana and Tunisia, clear similarities and differences become apparent. Each case demonstrates a unique approach to peace and democratization, influenced by different timelines, institutional setups, and relationships with external actors. Ghana exemplifies a relatively internal process towards democratic stability; Tunisia, a negotiated civic transition driven by strong societal pressure; and Sierra Leone, a model of externally supported democratic rebuilding. Despite these distinctions, common structural features remain: institutional legitimacy, inclusive political processes, the ability to broker compromises, and to channel political competition—all key factors in promoting a positive interaction between peace and democracy.

Ultimately, the peace–democracy relationship in political transitions has been understood through two main frameworks: a sequential model, where peace comes before democracy, and a co-constitutive process, where both develop together and reinforce each other. The following comparative outline highlights these paradigms—covering their mechanisms, strengths, and weaknesses—as shown by the cases of Ghana, Tunisia, and Sierra Leone.

While the sequential approach (e.g., post-conflict Sierra Leone) emphasizes security and stabilization before democratization, the co-constitutive model (e.g., Tunisia post-2011) demonstrates how hybrid institutions and inclusive participation can work together to strengthen peace and democratic legitimacy. This framework promotes moving beyond simple binary oppositions by viewing African transitions as

dialectical processes, where success depends less on fixed timelines and more on the interactions among local actors, structural reforms, and specific historical contexts.

Table 2 – National Configurations in the Peace–Democracy Nexus

Country	Post-crisis context	Dominant sequence	Key mechanisms of articulation	Observed outcomes	Limits / vulnerabilities
Ghana	End of military authoritarian regimes, constitutional transition (1992)	Gradual co-institutionalization	- Independent electoral commission- Active constitutional judiciary- Organized civil society	Peaceful alternation of power Growing democratic legitimacy	- Persistent clientelism- Partisan polarization during electoral cycles
Tunisia	Popular revolution (2011), collapse of authoritarian regime	Democracy as a vehicle of pacification	- National Dialogue (Quartet)- Inclusive constitution- Integration of opposition forces	Avoidance of civil war Post-revolutionary institutional stabilization	- Socioeconomic crisis- Political deadlock- Fragile rule of law
Sierra Leone	End of civil war (1991–2002), extended UN intervention	Peace first, externally guided democracy	- DDR and transitional justice- Internationally monitored elections- Restoration of state authority	Regular elections Gradual return to stability	- Weak institutions- Communal tensions- Dependency on foreign aid

This comparative framework highlights the diversity of crisis-exit trajectories and the different ways peace and democracy have been expressed in the cases of Ghana, Tunisia, and Sierra Leone. Ghana demonstrates a gradual, institution-led process of democratic consolidation, where mechanisms such as an independent electoral commission and an active judiciary have supported political stability. Tunisia, on the other hand, showcases a model where political pluralism served as a tool for post-revolutionary reconciliation, with the National Dialogue Quartet and an inclusive constitutional process playing key

roles in preventing civil war. Meanwhile, Sierra Leone shows how, in situations marked by extreme violence and institutional collapse, establishing minimal peace often comes before opening up democratic space. In this case, the sequence was heavily influenced by international involvement, with externally supported transitional justice and state-rebuilding efforts creating the foundation for later electoral processes. Overall, these cases emphasize that the relationship between peace and democracy does not follow a single pattern but depends on specific historical, institutional, and social contexts.

V. Comparative Analysis: Converging and Diverging Dynamics

The case studies discussed earlier reveal different paths of political change in post-conflict or post-authoritarian settings. This section suggests a cross-case analysis to find similarities and differences that shape the connection between peace and democracy. Four main analytical areas are used: the order of political events, the type of institutional setups, the role of domestic players, and the impact of international partners. A summary table at the end highlights the main features of each case across these variables, providing a visual overview of patterns and differences.

1. Sequencing: Peace before democracy, or a joint transition?

The cases examined demonstrate various sequences in how pacification and democratization relate to each other.

In Sierra Leone, peace comes before the democratic transition. The end of hostilities—rooted in a disarmament, demobilization, and reintegration (DDR) process and supported by a significant United Nations presence—created a minimal functional state before starting multiparty elections.

By contrast, Ghana's democratization was not sparked by civil war but resulted from a transition away from military authoritarian rule. In this context, pacification was not a prerequisite but a result of the democratic process itself, supported by increasing institutional legitimacy.

Tunisia exhibits a more hybrid progression: a sudden revolutionary break in 2011 was followed by rapid political liberalization. However, this swift opening led to intense polarization—especially between Islamist and secular groups. Only through an inclusive dialogue process, notably led by the National Dialogue Quartet, was the country able to stabilize its transition. Here, peace and democracy were built together in a cycle of crises and compromises.

These cases indicate that the sequence of peace and democracy is neither linear nor predetermined. Democracy can serve as a catalyst for pacification, just as peace can be a foundation for democratic development. What seems more essential is the ability of institutions to absorb and manage underlying conflicts—regardless of the order in which reforms occur.

2. Institutions: Between structural robustness and contextual adaptability

The strength and flexibility of institutions are crucial factors in the relationship between peace and democracy.

In Ghana, the presence of an independent electoral commission, a functioning judiciary, and constitutional oversight mechanisms has established a stable framework for political competition, decreasing the likelihood of violence.

In Tunisia, the slow institutionalization of democratic rules—despite a fragile security situation—was aided by inter-party dialogue and a broad consensus around the 2014 Constitution. However, ongoing institutional gridlocks highlight that formal legitimacy alone is not enough; it must be backed by perceived effectiveness.

In Sierra Leone, institutions were mostly rebuilt with international supervision. While this helped keep election processes neutral, the resulting external dependence and limited social ties of institutions restrict their long-term ability to resolve domestic conflicts.

These observations emphasize a dual requirement: institutional strength—characterized by independence, competence, and accessibility—and the capacity for contextual adaptation, which is the ability of institutions to reflect and respond to local sociopolitical realities.

3. Domestic Actors: Civil society, political elites, and moral leadership

Endogenous actors have played decisive roles in all three contexts.

In Ghana, civil society—especially faith-based organizations and independent media—has promoted electoral transparency and fostered a political culture rooted in respect for democratic norms. Moderate conduct by political elites during power transitions has also helped reduce tensions.

In Tunisia, the National Dialogue Quartet played a vital role in preventing violent escalation. These actors demonstrated credible moral leadership, capable of fostering trust among conflicting groups. The Tunisian case thus highlights the strategic importance of a well-organized civil society equipped with symbolic and institutional resources.

Sierra Leone, by contrast, exposes the limitations of a fragmented associational landscape. While some local organizations contributed to reconciliation and citizen participation, their influence remained limited due to resource constraints and restricted autonomy. However, the involvement of community and religious leaders occasionally compensated for the lack of structured actors.

This comparative insight confirms that the quality of local leadership, the degree of civil society organization, and the capacity to build inclusive coalitions are key success factors in promoting peace and democracy.

4. International Partners: Conditional support or structural dependence?

The role of international actors is both crucial and ambivalent.

In Sierra Leone, extensive UN and donor efforts facilitated swift pacification and a tightly monitored democratic transition. However, this strategy also created institutional reliance and restricted local control over reforms.

Tunisia, though receiving less direct assistance, still gained from targeted technical and financial support, especially from the European Union and the World Bank. This help strengthened institutional capacity without enforcing a strict external plan, maintaining some local independence.

In Ghana, international partners took a more discreet approach, emphasizing empowering civil society, promoting electoral transparency, and supporting governance reforms. This gradualist strategy seems to have contributed more sustainably to the strengthening of democracy.

Collectively, these cases indicate that international support can act as a catalyst—so long as it aligns with local dynamics, respects institutional timing, and prioritizes capacity-building over imposing external models.

To synthesize the insights from this cross-case analysis, the next section presents a comparative table structured around key variables. This typological matrix highlights both similarities and differences across the Ghanaian, Tunisian, and Sierra Leonean experiences, providing valuable analytical tools for theory development and policy formulation in post-crisis democratization.

Table 3: Comparative Trajectories of Peace and Democracy in Sierra Leone, Ghana, and Tunisia

Key Variables	Sierra Leone	Ghana	Tunisia
Starting Point of Transition	Post-conflict (civil war)	Post-authoritarian (military regime) transition	Revolutionary rupture (Arab Spring)
Dominant Sequencing	Peace → Democracy	Democracy → Consolidated Peace	Rupture → Dialogue → Democracy → Peace
Role of the International Community	Very strong (UN, UK, ECOWAS involvement)	Moderate (electoral observation, technical assistance)	Significant (EU, U.S., support for national dialogue)
Type of Peace	Negotiated, externally supported, post-conflict	Institutional and electoral peace	Peace through political compromise
Role of Civil Society	Modest but expanding	Central to electoral monitoring and mediation	Pivotal (National Dialogue Quartet)
Quality of Democratic Institutions	Under construction, fragile	Relatively robust and credible	In transition, with incomplete institutionalization

Key Variables	Sierra Leone	Ghana	Tunisia
Management of Identity Divisions	National reconciliation (TRC, DDR programs)	Strengthened national cohesion	Persistent tensions (ideological and social cleavages)
Mechanisms of Political Legitimation	Elections, Truth and Reconciliation Commission	Regular elections, political alternation	Constitution, national dialogue, pluralist elections
Durability of the Process	Fragile but resilient	Stable and consolidated	Ongoing, under pressure

This comparative overview of Sierra Leone, Ghana, and Tunisia highlights several common dynamics while also revealing important structural differences. These findings challenge the idea of a one-size-fits-all model for successful political transition and emphasize the need for a contextualized approach. Each path is shaped by a unique combination of historical legacies, institutional capacity, civil society engagement, and international involvement, showing that sustainable peace and democracy are best understood through a nuanced and case-specific perspective.

Having examined the distinct trajectories of political transitions in Sierra Leone, Ghana, and Tunisia, it is crucial to identify both the structural similarities and key differences that shape these processes. The following section provides a comparative analysis of these similarities and differences, offering a nuanced understanding of the complex relationship between peace and democracy in different contexts.

A. Structural Convergences

First, the three countries share a fundamental similarity: the central role of institutions in political stabilization. Whether through independent electoral commissions, constitutional courts, or mediation mechanisms, institutions have played a key role in managing tensions and strengthening the political system. These structures not only provide consistency in electoral processes but also build trust among political actors and the wider population in democratic rules.

Second, civil society emerged as a key actor in peacebuilding dynamics across all three cases. In Sierra Leone, local NGOs and religious groups supported social reintegration and memory work. Tunisia's national dialogue, led by the Quartet, was instrumental in

preventing the post-revolutionary state's collapse. Meanwhile, in Ghana, independent media and civic movements played crucial roles in democratic oversight and mediation during critical junctures.

Finally, all three transitions were supported by strategically deployed international engagement, though with varying levels of intensity. External aid helped stabilize public finances, oversee electoral processes, and support institutional reforms. However, the key difference is in how these interventions were adapted to local contexts.

B. Significant Divergences

Despite these similarities, the trajectories of Sierra Leone, Ghana, and Tunisia show significant differences, especially in the sequence of reforms. Sierra Leone exemplifies a peace-first approach, where post-conflict pacification came before political opening under strong international oversight. In contrast, Tunisia exhibits a more chaotic democratic transition that served as a pathway to peace through the gradual building of political consensus. Ghana, on the other hand, illustrates a process of democratic consolidation that successfully prevented major conflict after a long period of military rule.

Another key divergence concerns the perceived legitimacy of central authority. Tunisia's relatively inclusive transition still faces persistent social tensions and regional divisions that threaten stability. In Sierra Leone, legitimacy was strengthened by conflict resolution but remains fragile due to governance issues and corruption. Ghana's legitimacy rests on a competitive electoral system and growing respect for democratic change, although partisan tensions continue.

Finally, the involvement of political elites varies greatly. In Tunisia, political compromise between Islamist and secular forces was key to stability. Sierra Leone's elites often operated under constraints from peace agreements and external actors. In Ghana, elites gradually adopted democratic rules, promoting a political culture of peaceful competition.

C. Toward a Contextual Reading of Transitions

These observations support a contextual and relational view of the democracy-peace link. It is not about following a fixed sequence (peace → democracy or democracy → peace) but about finding internal factors that can create lasting changes. Political stability depends on

institutional legitimacy, the state's ability to meet social needs, and mutual recognition among political actors.

This insight calls for a critical reevaluation of international assistance approaches in transition processes. Comparative experience indicates that the effectiveness of external support relies less on its size or technical complexity and more on its ability to integrate into local realities, engage with endogenous social and institutional dynamics, and strengthen — rather than replace — national resilience mechanisms. Therefore, the concern is not about the amount of aid but its relevance, adaptability, and perceived legitimacy. Assistance that aligns with local timelines, values local expertise, and supports rather than rushes processes is more likely to sustainably reinforce fragile political balances.

VI. Conclusion and Policy Recommendations

The comparative analysis of political transitions in Sierra Leone, Ghana, and Tunisia challenges the commonly accepted dichotomy between peace and democracy in post-conflict and transitional contexts. Instead of viewing these stages as linear or sequential, these case studies show a dynamic co-creation of democratic consolidation and peacebuilding. This interdependence becomes especially effective when three key conditions are met: (1) institutions are regarded as legitimate by domestic actors; (2) truly inclusive participation mechanisms are established; and (3) both are embedded in the country's social and political fabric. Under these conditions, a positive cycle of mutual reinforcement between peace and democracy can emerge.

This research demonstrates that democracy can act as an effective tool for pacification, especially when it is rooted in participatory processes, fair electoral systems, and institutional safeguards that handle tensions effectively. Likewise, sustainable peace is not just the absence of violence; it requires a governance framework based on the rule of law, political pluralism, and the state's capacity to respond to societal demands.

The diversity of the three cases studied emphasizes that the relationship between peace and democracy is dependent on specific circumstances. In Sierra Leone, a strong international presence played a key role in establishing a post-conflict democratic order. Ghana, on the other hand, depended on internally driven institutional consolidation. Tunisia demonstrates that endogenous political

compromise—as exemplified by the National Dialogue Quartet—can lead to democratic stability even without an initial peacebuilding phase.

Policy Recommendations

Based on these findings, the following recommendations are suggested for African governments, international partners, and civil society actors:

1. Adopt a holistic approach that integrates peace and democracy: Avoid rigid sequential frameworks. Recognize that legitimate democratic institutions can serve as tools for political stabilization.
2. Strengthen institutional capacities before, during, and after elections: Electoral commissions, constitutional courts, and mediation bodies are vital in preventing political crises and building trust.
3. Promote local dialogue and mediation mechanisms: Support community-led initiatives for peaceful conflict resolution and inclusive consultation platforms (e.g., national forums, truth commissions, interparty dialogue spaces).
4. Avoid premature or forced democratization: Avoid imposing strict electoral schedules in fragile settings. Instead, encourage gradual transitions bolstered by capacity-building initiatives.
5. Ensure that international assistance aligns with local contexts: External aid should be tailored to locally expressed priorities and prevent disconnects between stabilization objectives and democratic aspirations.

Research Perspectives

This study opens avenues for future research on:

- Incomplete or reversible transitions (e.g., Mali, Sudan) to identify structural and political fault lines.
- The influence of transnational actors (diaspora communities, NGOs, private sector) on shaping peace and governance dynamics;

- Socioeconomic aspects of political transitions, particularly related to distributive justice and human security.

Ultimately, building democratic and peaceful political systems in Africa requires not only strong institutions but also a common vision of social coexistence based on inclusion, legitimacy, and shared conflict management. As Axel Honneth rightly states, “lasting peace is not merely a matter of institutions but of mutual recognition between equals” (*The Struggle for Recognition*, 1992). It is in this mutual recognition that the roots of a truly peaceful democracy can grow.

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